

In silico identification of putative drug targets in *Klebsiella pneumonia* MGH78578

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The prolonged use of antibiotics over the years has transformed many organisms into resistant to multiple drugs. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* MGH78578, a causative agent for respiratory and urinary tract infections, is one of the few Gram-negative bacteria, which has developed resistance to drugs. The present study was carried out to identify potential drug targets in *K. pneumonia* that might facilitate the discovery of novel drugs in near future. The present study has followed an *in silico* based approach for identification of drug targets. The comparison and analysis of proteomes of the causal organism and humans was made to screen out non-homologous proteins. Further, studies were carried out to list out essential proteins of the organism. KEGG pathway analysis was carried out to study the function of proteins. Different databases were used to find novel drug targets and various tools were used for the prediction of sub-cellular localization and membrane proteins. From the detailed analysis, 105 novel drug targets were identified, which have been involved in 24 specific pathways of *K. pneumoniae* MGH78578. Thirty nine proteins were predicted as outer membrane proteins, which could be used as potential vaccine candidates.

Keywords: BLAST, DEG, homologous proteins, KAAS server, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, potential drug targets, reverse vaccinology

Introduction

In the past decade, complete genome sequences of several microbes are worked out¹. And comparative genomics and subtractive genomics approaches have been used to retrieve valuable information for finding the treatment of various infections caused by the pathogens². The critical genes crucial for the survival of pathogen and absent in the host³ are also identified using the subtractive genomics approach. The chances of cross-reactivity and side-effects⁴ are minimized by selecting such non-homologous proteins which are not present in humans. The genes and their products which can be used as potential drug targets are also identified by analyzing these genes with the KEGG pathway database⁵.

The search for novel drug targets relies on the genomics data. The comparative genomics approach can be used for selecting non-homologous genes coding for proteins, which are present in pathogens but not in the host. For identifying such genes, BLAST against the human genome can be performed using BLASTP program. This eliminates the

homologous genes present in the humans. Thereafter, the critical genes required for the survival of the pathogen can be identified using DEG⁶. Such approach will ensure that the drug target is available only in the pathogen and not in the humans. Using such approach, novel targets have been identified successfully for various pathogens⁷⁻¹⁷.

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a Gram-negative, non-motile, encapsulated, lactose fermenting, facultative anaerobic, rod shaped bacterium found in the normal flora of the mouth, skin, and intestine¹⁸. *Klebsiella* infection occurs in lungs, skin, pharynx, or gastrointestinal tract. It is the second common causative agent for urinary tract infections after *Escherichia coli*. Pneumonia develops when the bacilli invade and multiply within the alveolar spaces.

Several drugs like cefotaxime, ceftriaxone, gentamicin, amikacin, imipenem, cilastatin, ciprofloxacin, aztreonam, trimethoprim and sulfamethoxazole¹⁹⁻²³, having many side-effects, are reported to be ineffective against *K. pneumoniae*. Hence, it is the need of the hour to explore the possibility of identification of novel drug targets and designing of drugs against *K. pneumoniae*. It can be possible now due to the availability of proteomes of the pathogen. In the present study, the proteome of the

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K. pneumoniae MGH78578 was analyzed. The computational approach, based on subtractive genomics, has been used successfully in earlier studies for finding putative drug targets⁷⁻¹¹.

Materials and Methods

In the present investigation, multidrug resistant *K. pneumoniae* MGH78578 was selected. Its genome was sequenced by Washington University Genome Sequencing Centre. The proteome of MGH78578 (Taxon Identification: 272620) was downloaded from UniProt (www.uniprot.org). The proteins having sequence lengths less than 100 amino acids were eliminated as they are less likely to represent essential genes¹⁰.

The *K. pneumoniae* proteins were analyzed using CD-HIT to identify the paralogous or duplicate proteins. Sequence identity cut-off was kept at 0.6 (60% identity) and global sequence identity algorithm was selected for alignment of the amino acids; a bandwidth of 20 amino acids and default parameters for alignment coverage were selected^{24,25}. These proteins were subjected to BLAST against Human genome (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/seq/BlastGen/BlastGen.cgi?taxid=9606>) with expectation value (E-value) of 10^{-4} and for the purpose Refseq protein database was selected. To search the homologous proteins between *K. pneumoniae* and host, BlastP program was used. The obtained homologous protein sets were eliminated and the resultant dataset was non-homologous with humans²⁶⁻³¹. DEG (<http://tubic.tju.edu.cn/deg/>) was performed to identify the critical genes necessary for the survival of the *K. pneumoniae*. A random E-value was kept as 10^{-4} ; minimum bit-score cut-off of 100; BLOSUM62 matrix and gapped alignment mode were selected to screen out the essential proteins^{32,33}. Metabolic pathway analysis of the essential proteins of *K. pneumoniae* was done by KAAS (KEGG Automatic Annotation Server) (www.genome.jp/tools/kaas/). KAAS provides functional annotations of genes by BLAST comparison against the manually curated KEGG Genes database. The result contains KO (KEGG Orthology) assignments and automatically generated KEGG pathways³⁴. KEGG pathway studies were also conducted to analyze the occurrence of alternate pathways, after which the proteins were selected as potential drug targets. This enabled to predict the protein function and genome annotation, and potential targets were identified. Screening of the potential drug targets was carried out

by similarity search using protein sequence of all the potential targets against the DrugBank³⁵, TTD³⁶, PDTD³⁷ and HIT³⁸ to reach the novel drug targets. Additionally, using computational methods, the subcellular localization of the protein by psortb v3.0³⁹ and outer membrane proteins by Trans Membrane prediction using hidden Markov models (TMHMM)⁴⁰ were predicted to identify the surface membrane proteins, which could be used as probable vaccine candidates. Psortb generates prediction results for five major localizations for Gram-negative bacteria (cytoplasmic, inner membrane, periplasmic, outer membrane and extracellular). TMHMM is a program for predicting transmembrane helices based on a hidden Markov model, and it reads a FASTA formatted protein sequence and predicts locations of transmembrane, intracellular and extracellular regions.

Results and Discussion

In silico subtractive genomics approach is a powerful-method to identify the specific genes, which are present in the pathogen but absent in the host. This helps in the identification of novel organism specific genes, which can be used as drug targets¹². *In silico* drug target identification mainly relies on the principle that “a good drug target is a gene essential for the bacterial survival yet cannot be found in host”¹³.

In the present study, non-human homolog essential genes of *K. pneumoniae* as well as their protein products have been identified using subtractive genomic approach, which are likely to lead to the development of drugs that strongly bind with the pathogen. The *K. pneumoniae* MGH78578 consists of 5126 proteins which were downloaded from UniProt database (<http://www.uniprot.org/uniprot/?query=organism:272620+keyword:181>). The homologous proteins were identified using 60% identity as threshold with the CD-HIT tool. Out of the 5126 proteins, 664 duplicate proteins were found. Remaining 4462 proteins were analyzed with the help of BLAST against human using BLASTP. This revealed 2321 proteins with no significant similarity with human proteins. By using the Database of essential Genes (DEG), 453 critical proteins were identified. These proteins were analyzed using KAAS server. Detailed pathway analysis revealed that 345 proteins were such that even after targeting them the organism could survive. In other words, these proteins could not act as a drug target. Hence, these proteins

were removed and 108 proteins very crucial for the survival of the organism were identified (Fig. 1). Screening of the drug targets was carried out using DrugBank, TTD, PDTD and HIT for the 108 proteins identified from the pathway analysis. Of the 108 proteins, only 3 proteins were used for the drug target: DNA-directed RNA polymerase subunit α [EC:2.7.7.6] involved in the purine and pyrimidine metabolism), large subunit ribosomal protein L22 (RP-L22, rplV) and small subunit ribosomal protein S13 (RP-S13, rpsM) responsible for protein synthesis. Among the three said proteins, Rifabutin (DrugBank ID: DB00615) targets the first one, and Azithromycin (DrugBank ID: DB00207), Erythromycin (DrugBank ID: DB00199), Quinupristin (DrugBank ID: DB01369) and Tigecycline (DrugBank ID: DB00560) target the remaining two.

Succinate dehydrogenase hydrophobic membrane anchor protein (sdhD) is involved in energy metabolisms [citrate cycle (TCA cycle), oxidative phosphorylation, carbon fixation in prokaryotes] and two-component system. In the present study, 32 unique pathways/biological processes were found, of which 24 pathways/biological processes were catalyzed by the proteins, which could be selected as drug target (Table 1). These 24 pathways/biological processes are classified into 10 classes: (i) Biosynthesis (lipopolysaccharide, peptidoglycan, fatty acid, siderophore group nonribosomal peptides, ubiquinone and other terpenoid-quinone, glycerophospholipid, D-glutamine and D-glutamate biosynthesis), (ii) Nucleic acid metabolism (purine and pyrimidine metabolism, DNA replication, homologous recombination and mismatch repair), (iii) Energy metabolism [citrate cycle (TCA cycle), carbon fixation in prokaryotes and oxidative phosphorylation], (iv) Amino acid metabolism (valine, leucine and isoleucine biosynthesis), (v) Vitamin metabolism (riboflavin and biotin metabolism), (vi) Ribosome, (vii) Phosphotransferase system (PTS), (viii) ABC transporters, (ix) Two-component system, and (x) Bacterial secretion and protein export system (Pathway details; see supplementary data).

The proteins involved in the remaining 8 pathways/biological processes were found to have no significance to act as a drug target or have alternative pathway to produce its product: (i) Amino sugar and nucleotide sugar metabolism, (ii) Butanoate metabolism, (iii) C5-branched dibasic acid metabolism, (iv) Fructose and mannose metabolism, (v) Glycolysis/gluconeogenesis, (vi) Pantothenate and

CoA biosynthesis, (vii) Starch and sucrose metabolism, and (viii) Toluene degradation. So, these proteins were eliminated⁷⁻¹⁷ (Pathway details; see supplementary data).

Thus, of the 108 proteins, 105 were novel proteins (Fig. 2), in which 13 proteins were reported as research targets for various pathogens: UDP-N-acetylglucosamine-N-acetylmuramyl-(pentapeptide) pyrophosphoryl-undecaprenol N-acetylglucosamine transferase [EC:2.4.1.227] (murG) involved in peptidoglycan biosynthesis⁴¹; the proteins involved in two-component systems are OmpR family proteins (sensor histidine kinase PhoQ [EC:2.7.13.3], BaeS [EC:2.7.13.3] and response regulator PhoP, CpxR, BaeR), NarL family proteins (capsular synthesis sensor histidine kinase RcsC [EC:2.7.13.3], EvgS [EC:2.7.13.3], response regulator EvgA and NtrC family (response regulator HydG)^{42,43}; the proteins

Fig. 1—Summary of target identification

Fig. 2—Percentage distribution of 105 novel drug targets involved in different metabolic pathways/biological process

Table 1—Novel drug targets involved in different metabolic pathways and other cellular activities

No.	KEGG Orthology number (ko), Gene and Protein Name
1.	Biosynthesis (Lipopolysaccharide, Peptidoglycan, Fatty acid, siderophore group non-ribosomal peptides, Ubiquinone and other terpenoid-quinone, Glycerophospholipid, D-Glutamine & D-glutamate Biosynthesis) Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 1)
	1. ko:K01252 entB; enterobactin isochorismatase [EC:3.3.2.1]
	2. ko:K01924 murC; UDP-N-acetylmuramate--alanine ligase [EC:6.3.2.8]
	3. ko:K01925 murD; UDP-N-acetylmuramoylalanine--D-glutamate ligase [EC:6.3.2.9]
	4. ko:K01929 murF; UDP-N-acetylmuramoylalanine--D-glutamyl-2,6-diaminopimelate--D-alanyl-D-alanine ligase [EC:6.3.2.10]
	5. ko:K02361 entC; isochorismate synthase [EC:5.4.4.2]
	6. ko:K02371 fabK; enoyl-[acyl carrier protein] reductase II [EC:1.3.1.-]
	7. ko:K02527 kdtA; 3-deoxy-D-manno-oculosonic-acid transferase [EC:2.-.-.-]
	8. ko:K02536 lpxD; UDP-3-O-[3-hydroxymyristoyl] glucosamine N-acyltransferase [EC:2.3.1.-]
	9. ko:K02552 menF; menaquinone-specific isochorismate synthase [EC:5.4.4.2]
	10. ko:K02563 murG; UDP-N-acetylglucosamine--N-acetylmuramyl-(pentapeptide) pyrophosphoryl-undecaprenol N-acetylglucosamine transferase [EC:2.4.1.227]
	11. ko:K02844 waaG, rfaG; UDP-glucose:(heptosyl)LPS alpha-1,3-glucosyltransferase [EC:2.4.1.-]
	12. ko:K02849 waaQ, rfaQ; heptosyltransferase III [EC:2.4.-.-]
	13. ko:K03980 mviN; virulence factor
	14. ko:K06131 cls; cardiolipin synthase [EC:2.7.8.-]
2.	Nucleic acid Metabolism (Purine & Pyrimidine metabolism, DNA replication, Homologous recombination and Mismatch repair) Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 2)
	1. ko:K01141 E3.1.11.1, sbcB; exodeoxyribonuclease I [EC:3.1.11.1]
	2. ko:K02314 dnaB; replicative DNA helicase [EC:3.6.4.12]
	3. ko:K02316 dnaG; DNA primase [EC:2.7.7.-]
	4. ko:K02317 dnaT; DNA replication protein DnaT
	5. ko:K02337 DPO3A1, dnaE; DNA polymerase III subunit alpha [EC:2.7.7.7]
	6. ko:K02338 DPO3B, dnaN; DNA polymerase III subunit beta [EC:2.7.7.7]
	7. ko:K02339 DPO3C, holC; DNA polymerase III subunit chi [EC:2.7.7.7]
	8. ko:K02340 DPO3D1, holA; DNA polymerase III subunit delta [EC:2.7.7.7]
	9. ko:K02342 DPO3E, dnaQ; DNA polymerase III subunit epsilon [EC:2.7.7.7]
	10. ko:K02344 DPO3P, holD; DNA polymerase III subunit psi [EC:2.7.7.7]
	11. ko:K03470 rnhB; ribonuclease HII [EC:3.1.26.4]
	12. ko:K03581 recD; exodeoxyribonuclease V alpha subunit [EC:3.1.11.5]
	13. ko:K03582 recB; exodeoxyribonuclease V beta subunit [EC:3.1.11.5]
	14. ko:K03629 recF; DNA replication and repair protein RecF
	15. ko:K03657 uvrD, pcrA; DNA helicase II / ATP-dependent DNA helicase PcrA [EC:3.6.4.12]
	16. ko:K04066 priA; primosomal protein N' (replication factor Y) (superfamily II helicase)[EC:3.6.4.-]
	17. ko:K04067 priC; primosomal replication protein N
	18. ko:K06223 dam; DNA adenine methylase [EC:2.1.1.72]
	19. ko:K10857 exoX; exodeoxyribonuclease X [EC:3.1.11.-]
3.	Energy Metabolism (Citrate cycle (TCA cycle), Carbon fixation in prokaryotes & Oxidative phosphorylation) Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 3)
	1. ko:K00242 sdhD; succinate dehydrogenase hydrophobic membrane anchor protein
	2. ko:K00247 frdD; fumarate reductase subunit D
	3. ko:K00425 cydA; cytochrome bd-I oxidase subunit I [EC:1.10.3.-]
	4. ko:K00426 cydB; cytochrome bd-I oxidase subunit II [EC:1.10.3.-]
	5. ko:K01507 E3.6.1.1, ppa; inorganic pyrophosphatase [EC:3.6.1.1]
	6. ko:K02109 ATPF0B, atpF; F-type H ⁺ -transporting ATPase subunit b [EC:3.6.3.14]
	7. ko:K02300 cyoD; cytochrome o ubiquinol oxidase operon protein cyoD
4.	Amino acid Metabolism (Valine, leucine and isoleucine biosynthesis) Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 4)
	1. ko:K01653 E2.2.1.6S, ilvH, ilvN; acetolactate synthase I/III small subunit [EC:2.2.1.6]
5.	Vitamin Metabolism (Riboflavin & Biotin metabolism) Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 5)
	1. ko:K00794 ribH; riboflavin synthase beta chain [EC:2.5.1.-]
	2. ko:K01012 E2.8.1.6, bioB; biotin synthetase [EC:2.8.1.6]

Table 1—Novel drug targets involved in different metabolic pathways and other cellular activities—*Contd.*

No.	KEGG Orthology number (ko), Gene and Protein Name
6.	Ribosomal Proteins Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 6) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> ko:K02863 RP-L1, rplA; large subunit ribosomal protein L1 ko:K02876 RP-L15, rplO; large subunit ribosomal protein L15 ko:K02881 RP-L18, rplR; large subunit ribosomal protein L18 ko:K02884 RP-L19, rplS; large subunit ribosomal protein L19 ko:K02888 RP-L21, rplU; large subunit ribosomal protein L21 ko:K02895 RP-L24, rplX; large subunit ribosomal protein L24 ko:K02933 RP-L6, rplF; large subunit ribosomal protein L6 ko:K02935 RP-L7, rplL; large subunit ribosomal protein L7/L12 ko:K02939 RP-L9, rplI; large subunit ribosomal protein L9 ko:K02990 RP-S6, rpsF; small subunit ribosomal protein S6 ko:K02994 RP-S8, rpsH; small subunit ribosomal protein S8
7.	Phosphotransferase system (PTS) Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 7) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> ko:K02759 PTS-Cel-EIIA, celC; PTS system, cellobiose-specific IIA component [EC:2.7.1.69] ko:K02760 PTS-Cel-EIIB, celA; PTS system, cellobiose-specific IIB component [EC:2.7.1.69] ko:K02777 PTS-Glc-EIIA, crr; PTS system, glucose-specific IIA component [EC:2.7.1.69] ko:K02794 PTS-Man-EIIB, manX; PTS system, mannose-specific IIB component [EC:2.7.1.69] ko:K08483 PTS-EI.PTSI, ptsI; phosphotransferase system, enzyme I, PtsI [EC:2.7.3.9] ko:K08484 PTS-EI.PTSP, ptsP; phosphotransferase system, enzyme I, PtsP [EC:2.7.3.9]
8.	ABC transporters Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 8) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> ko:K02033 ABC.PE.P; peptide/nickel transport system permease protein ko:K02034 ABC.PE.P1; peptide/nickel transport system permease protein ko:K02035 ABC.PE.S; peptide/nickel transport system substrate-binding protein ko:K02046 cysU; sulfate transport system permease protein ko:K07091 lptF; lipopolysaccharide export system permease protein ko:K09686 ABC-2.AB.P; antibiotic transport system permease protein ko:K09690 ABC-2.LPSE.P; lipopolysaccharide transport system permease protein ko:K09808 ABC.LPT.P, lolC, lolE; lipoprotein-releasing system permease protein ko:K09811 ftsX; cell division transport system permease protein ko:K09815 znuA; zinc transport system substrate-binding protein ko:K10009 ABC.CYST.P; cystine transport system permease protein ko:K10014 hisJ; histidine transport system substrate-binding protein ko:K10439 rbsB; ribose transport system substrate-binding protein ko:K11082 phnV; 2-aminoethylphosphonate transport system permease protein ko:K11720 lptG; lipopolysaccharide export system permease protein ko:K12368 dppA; dipeptide transport system substrate-binding protein
9.	Two-component system Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 9) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> ko:K00247 frdD; fumarate reductase subunit D ko:K02313 dnaA; chromosomal replication initiator protein ko:K03092 SIG54, rpoN; RNA polymerase sigma-54 factor ko:K07637 phoQ; two-component system, OmpR family, sensor histidine kinase PhoQ [EC:2.7.13.3] ko:K07642 baeS; two-component system, OmpR family, sensor histidine kinase BaeS [EC:2.7.13.3] ko:K07645 qseC; two-component system, OmpR family, sensor histidine kinase QseC [EC:2.7.13.3] ko:K07660 phoP; two-component system, OmpR family, response regulator PhoP ko:K07662 cpxR; two-component system, OmpR family, response regulator CpxR ko:K07664 baeR; two-component system, OmpR family, response regulator BaeR ko:K07677 rcsC; two-component system, NarL family, capsular synthesis sensor histidine kinase RcsC [EC:2.7.13.3] ko:K07679 evgS, bvgS; two-component system, NarL family, sensor histidine kinase EvgS [EC:2.7.13.3] ko:K07690 evgA, bvgA; two-component system, NarL family, response regulator EvgA ko:K07713 hydG, zraR; two-component system, NtrC family, response regulator HydG ko:K07803 zraP; zinc resistance-associated protein

Contd.

Table 1—Novel drug targets involved in different metabolic pathways and other cellular activities—*Contd*

No. KEGG Orthology number (ko), Gene and Protein Name

10. Secretion & Protein export system (Bacterial secretion & Protein export system)

Supplementary Data (Metabolic pathway Fig. 10)

1. ko:K02454 gspE; general secretion pathway protein E
2. ko:K02455 gspF; general secretion pathway protein F
3. ko:K02456 gspG; general secretion pathway protein G
4. ko:K03070 secA; preprotein translocase subunit SecA
5. ko:K03071 secB; preprotein translocase subunit SecB
6. ko:K03072 secD; preprotein translocase subunit SecD
7. ko:K03073 secE; preprotein translocase subunit SecE
8. ko:K03074 secF; preprotein translocase subunit SecF
9. ko:K03076 secY; preprotein translocase subunit SecY
10. ko:K03100 lepB; signal peptidase I [EC:3.4.21.89]
11. ko:K03118 tatC; sec-independent protein translocase protein TatC
12. ko:K03210 yajC; preprotein translocase subunit YajC
13. ko:K03217 yidC, spoIIIJ, OXA1; preprotein translocase subunit YidC
14. ko:K11903, hcp; type VI secretion system secreted protein Hcp
15. ko:K12340 tolC; outer membrane channel protein TolC
16. ko:K13301 secM; secretion monitor

involved in phosphotransferase system are enzyme I, PtsI (EC:2.7.3.9), enzyme I, PtsP [EC:2.7.3.9]⁴⁴ and signal peptidase I (lepB) [EC:3.4.21.89]⁴⁵.

Computational prediction of bacterial protein subcellular localization (SCL) provides a quick and inexpensive means for gaining insight into protein function, verifying experimental results, annotating newly sequenced bacterial genomes, and detecting potential cell surface/secreted drug targets⁴⁶. The protein localization study revealed that among the 108 predicted drug targets, 54 proteins were present in cytoplasm, 41 in cell membrane and 6 in periplasm, and for 7 proteins localization could not be predicted. Reverse vaccinology is an emerging vaccine development approach that starts with the prediction of vaccine targets by bioinformatics analysis of microbial genome sequences⁴⁷. Subcellular location is considered as one of the main criteria for vaccine target prediction. However, other criteria have also been considered. For example, since the outer membrane proteins containing more than one transmembrane helix were difficult to clone and purify⁴⁸, the number of transmembrane domain is often considered for screening the proteins as a vaccine candidate. So, in the present study, a total 39 outer membrane proteins were identified, of which 11 were identified as having one or less than one transmembrane helix (Table 2): UDP-N-acetylglucosamine--N-acetylmuramyl-(pentapeptide)

pyrophosphoryl-undecaprenol N-acetylglucosamine transferase [EC:2.4.1.227] (murG), preprotein translocase subunit SecA, UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-lanyl-D-glutamyl-2,6-diaminopime-late--D-alanyl-D-alanine ligase [EC:6.3.2.10] (murF), heptosyltransferase III [EC:2.4.-.-] (waaQ, rfaQ), exodeoxyribonuclease I [EC:3.1.11.1] (sbcB), outer membrane channel protein TolC, F-type H⁺-transporting ATPase subunit b [EC:3.6.3.14] (atpF), two-component system-OmpR family-sensor histidine kinase QseC [EC:2.7.13.3] (qseC & evgS), NarL family-sensor histidine kinase EvgS [EC:2.7.13.3], preprotein translocase subunit YajC, and general secretion pathway protein G (gspG). These proteins could be cloned and over expressed to study the possibilities of the vaccine candidates.

Conclusion

The *in silico* based approach involves a series of screening of proteins that can be used as potential drug targets and vaccine candidates. The targets found are inevitable for the growth of the organisms and these proteins neither have a substitute protein nor an alternative pathway to accomplish the process. The current study can be carried forward to design a drug that can block these targeted proteins. The microorganisms are fast gaining resistance to the existing drugs, so designing better and effective drugs need a faster method.

Table. 2—List of predicted outer membrane proteins

No. KEGG Orthology number (ko), Gene and Protein Name

Outer membrane proteins with one or less than one transmembrane helix

1. ko:K02563 murG; UDP-N-acetylglucosamine--N-acetylmuramyl-(pentapeptide) pyrophosphoryl-undecaprenol N-acetylglucosamine transferase [EC:2.4.1.227]
2. ko:K03070 secA; preprotein translocase subunit SecA
3. ko:K01929 murF; UDP-N-acetylmuramoylalanyl-D-glutamyl-2,6-diaminopimelate--D-alanyl-D-alanine ligase [EC:6.3.2.10]
4. ko:K02849 waaQ, rfaQ; heptosyltransferase III [EC:2.4.-.-]
5. ko:K01141 E3.1.11.1, sbcB; exodeoxyribonuclease I [EC:3.1.11.1]
6. ko:K12340 tolC; outer membrane channel protein TolC
7. ko:K02109 ATPF0B, atpF; F-type H+-transporting ATPase subunit b [EC:3.6.3.14]
8. ko:K07645 qseC; two-component system, OmpR family, sensor histidine kinase QseC [EC:2.7.13.3]
9. ko:K07679 evgS, bvgS; two-component system, NarL family, sensor histidine kinase EvgS [EC:2.7.13.3]
10. ko:K03210 yajC; preprotein translocase subunit YajC
11. ko:K02456 gspG; general secretion pathway protein G

Outer membrane proteins with more than one transmembrane helix

12. ko:K06131 cls; cardiolipin synthase [EC:2.7.8.-]
13. ko:K07637 phoQ; two-component system, OmpR family, sensor histidine kinase PhoQ [EC:2.7.13.3]
14. ko:K07642 baeS; two-component system, OmpR family, sensor histidine kinase BaeS [EC:2.7.13.3]
15. ko:K07677 rcsC; two-component system, NarL family, capsular synthesis sensor histidine kinase RcsC [EC:2.7.13.3]
16. ko:K03100 lepB; signal peptidase I [EC:3.4.21.89]
17. ko:K00247 frdD; fumarate reductase subunit D
18. ko:K00242 sdhD; succinate dehydrogenase hydrophobic membrane anchor protein
19. ko:K10009 ABC.CYST.P; cystine transport system permease protein
20. ko:K03073 secE; preprotein translocase subunit SecE
21. ko:K02455 gspF; general secretion pathway protein F
22. ko:K02300 cyoD; cytochrome o ubiquinol oxidase operon protein cyoD
23. ko:K03217 yidC, spoIIIJ, OXA1; preprotein translocase subunit YidC
24. ko:K09808 ABC.LPT.P, lolC, lolE; lipoprotein-releasing system permease protein
25. ko:K09811 ftsX; cell division transport system permease protein
26. ko:K03072 secD; preprotein translocase subunit SecD
27. ko:K11720 lptG; lipopolysaccharide export system permease protein
28. ko:K07091 lptF; lipopolysaccharide export system permease protein
29. ko:K09686 ABC-2.AB.P; antibiotic transport system permease protein
30. ko:K09690 ABC-2.LPSE.P; lipopolysaccharide transport system permease protein
31. ko:K03074 secF; preprotein translocase subunit SecF
32. ko:K03118 tatC; sec-independent protein translocase protein TatC
33. ko:K02033 ABC.PE.P; peptide/nickel transport system permease protein
34. ko:K02034 ABC.PE.P1; peptide/nickel transport system permease protein
35. ko:K00426 cydB; cytochrome bd-I oxidase subunit II [EC:1.10.3.-]
36. ko:K02046 cysU; sulfate transport system permease protein
37. ko:K00425 cydA; cytochrome bd-I oxidase subunit I [EC:1.10.3.-]
38. ko:K03076 secY; preprotein translocase subunit SecY
39. ko:K03980 mviN; virulence factor

References

- 1 De Groot A S, Sbai H, Aubin C S, McMurray J & Martin W, Immuno-informatics-mining the genomes for vaccine components, *Immunol Cell Biol*, 80 (2002) 255-269.
- 2 Galperin M Y & Koonin E V, Searching for drug targets in microbial genomes, *Curr Opin Biotechnol*, 10 (1999) 571-578.
- 3 Koonin E V, Tatusov R L & Galperin M Y, Beyond complete genomes: From sequence to structure and function, *Curr Opin Struc Biol*, 8 (1998) 355-363.
- 4 Barh D, Tiwari S, Jain N, Ali A, Santos A R *et al*, *In silico* subtractive genomics for target identification in human bacterial pathogens, *Drug Develop Res*, 72 (2011) 162-177. (DOI: 10.1002/ddr.20413)
- 5 Moriya Y, Itoh M, Okuda S, Yoshizawa A C & Kanehisa M, KAAS: An automatic genome annotation and pathway reconstruction server, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 35 (2007) W182-185.
- 6 Zhang R & Lin Y, DEG 5.0, a database of essential genes in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 37 (2009), D455-D458.
- 7 Amineni U, Pradhan D & Marisetty H, *In silico* identification of common putative drug targets in *Leptospira interrogans*, *J Chem Biol*, 3 (2010) 165-173.
- 8 Rathi B, Sarangi A N & Trivedi N, Genome subtraction for novel target definition in *Salmonella typhi*, *Bioinformatics*, 4 (2009) 143-150.
- 9 Koteswara Reddy G, Nagamalleswara Rao K, Phani Rama Krishna B & Aravind S, *In silico* identification of potential

- therapeutic targets in *Clostridium botulinum* by the approach subtractive genomics, *Int J Bioinform Res*, 2 (2010) 12-16.
- 10 Dutta A, Singh S K, Ghosh P, Mukherjee R, Mitter S *et al*, *In silico* identification of potential therapeutic targets in the human pathogen *Helicobacter pylori*, *In Silico Biol*, 6 (2006) 43-47.
 - 11 Sakharkar K R, Sakharkar M K & Chow V T, A novel genomics approach for the identification of drug targets in pathogens with special reference to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *In Silico Biol*, 4 (2004) 355-360.
 - 12 Gupta S K, Singh S, Gupta M K, Pant K K & Seth P K, Definition of potential targets in *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* through subtractive genome analysis, *J Antivir Antiretrovir*, 2 (2010) 38-42.
 - 13 Allsop A E, Brooks G, Bruton G, Coulton S, Edwards P D *et al*, Penem inhibitors of bacterial signal peptidase, *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*, 5 (1995) 443-448.
 - 14 Sharma V, Gupta P & Dixit A. *In silico* identification of putative drug targets from different metabolic pathways of *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *In Silico Biol*, 8 (2008) 331-338.
 - 15 Barh D & Kumar A. *In silico* identification of candidate drug and vaccine targets from various pathways in *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *In Silico Biol*, 9 (2009) 225-231.
 - 16 Singh S, Malik B K & Sharma D K. Metabolic pathway analysis of *S. pneumoniae*: An *in silico* approach towards drug-design, *J Bioinform Comput Biol*, 5 (2007) 135-53.
 - 17 Anishetty S, Pulimi M & Pennathur G, Potential drug targets in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* through metabolic pathway analysis, *Comput Biol Chem*, 29 (2005) 368-378.
 - 18 Ryan K J & Ray C G, *Sherris medical microbiology*, 4th edn (McGraw Hill Book Publishing Co, New York) 2004.
 - 19 *AHFS drug information* (American Society of Health-System Pharmacists, Bethesda, MD) 2006.
 - 20 Rich M, Ritterhoff R & Hoffmann R, A fatal case of aplastic anemia following chloramphenicol (chloromycetin) therapy, *Ann Intern Med*, 33 (1950) 1459-1467.
 - 21 Schaeffer A J, Co-trimoxazole use restricted, *Drug Ther Bull*, 33 (1995) 92-93.
 - 22 De Champs C, Rich C, Chandezon P, Chanal C, Sirot D *et al*, Factors associated with antimicrobial resistance among clinical isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: 1-year survey in a French University hospital, *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis*, 23 (2004) 456-462.
 - 23 Hasdemir U O, Chevalier J, Nordmann P & Pagès J M, Detection and prevalence of active drug efflux mechanism in various multidrug-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains from Turkey, *J Clin Microbiol*, 42 (2004) 2701-2706.
 - 24 Huang Y, Niu B, Gao Y, Fu L & Li W, CD-HIT Suite: A web server for clustering and comparing biological sequences, *Bioinformatics*, 26 (2010) 680-682.
 - 25 Li W & Godzik A, Cd-hit: A fast program for clustering and comparing large sets of protein or nucleotide sequences, *Bioinformatics*, 22 (2006) 1658-1659.
 - 26 Kerfeld C A & Scott K M, Using BLAST to Teach "E-value-ationary" concepts, *PLoS Biol*, 9 (2011) e1001014.
 - 27 Waterman M S & Vingron M, Rapid and accurate estimates of statistical significance for sequence data base searches, *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 91 (1994) 4625-4628.
 - 28 Collins J F, Coulson A F & Lyall A, The significance of protein sequence similarities, *Comput Appl Biosci*, 4 (1988) 67-71.
 - 29 Altschul S F, Gish W, Miller W, Myers E W & Lipman D J, Basic local alignment search tool, *J Mol Biol*, 215 (1990) 403-410.
 - 30 Pearson W R, Effective protein sequence comparison. *Methods Enzymol*, 266 (1996) 227-258.
 - 31 Pearson W R, Comparison of methods for searching protein sequence databases, *Protein Sci*, 4 (1995) 1145-1160.
 - 32 Zhang R & Lin Y, DEG 5.0: A database of essential genes in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 37 (2009), D455-D458.
 - 33 Zhang C-T & Zhang R, Gene essentiality analysis based on DEG, a database of essential genes, *Methods Mol Biol*, 416 (2008) 391-400.
 - 34 Moriya Y, Itoh M, Okuda S, Yoshizawa A C & Kanehisa M, KAAS: An automatic genome annotation and pathway reconstruction server, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 35 (2007) 182-185.
 - 35 Knox C, Law V, Jewison T, Liu P, Ly S *et al*, DrugBank 3.0: A comprehensive resource for 'omics' research on drugs, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 39 (2011) D1035-D1041.
 - 36 Chen X, Ji Z L & Chen Y Z, TTD: Therapeutic target database, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 30 (2002) 412-415.
 - 37 Gao Z, Li H, Zhang H, Liu X, Kang L *et al*, PDTD: A web-accessible protein database for drug target identification, *BMC Bioinformatics*, 9 (2008) 104.
 - 38 Ye H, Ye L, Kang H, Zhang D, Tao L *et al*, HIT: Linking herbal active ingredients to targets, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 39 (2011) D1055-D1059.
 - 39 Yu N Y, Wagner J R, Laird M R, Melli G, Rey S *et al*, PSORTb 3.0: Improved protein subcellular localization prediction with refined localization subcategories and predictive capabilities for all prokaryotes, *Bioinformatics*, 26 (2010) 1608-1615.
 - 40 Krogh A, Larsson B, von Heijne G & Sonnhammer E L, Predicting transmembrane protein topology with a hidden Markov model: Application to complete genomes, *J Mol Biol*, 305 (2001) 567-580.
 - 41 Hu Y, Helm J S, Chen L, Ginsberg C, Gross B *et al*, Identification of selective inhibitors for the glycosyltransferase MurG via high-throughput screening, *Chem Biol*, 11 (2004) 703-711.
 - 42 Matsushita M & Janda K D, Histidine kinases as targets for new antimicrobial agents, *Bioorg Med Chem*, 10 (2002) 855-867.
 - 43 Selitrennikoff C P, Alex L, Miller T K, Clemons K V, Simon M I *et al*, COS-I, a putative two-component histidine kinase of *Candida albicans*, is an *in vivo* virulence factor, *Med Mycol*, 39 (2001) 69-74.
 - 44 Labischinski H & Johannsen L, Cell wall targets in methicillin-resistant staphylococci, *Drug Resist Updat*, 2 (1999) 319-325.
 - 45 Kulanthaivel P, Kreuzman A J, Stregre M A, Belvo M D, Smitka T A *et al*, Novel lipoglycopeptides as inhibitors of bacterial signal peptidase I, *J Biol Chem*, 279 (2004) 36250-36258.
 - 46 Gardy J L & Brinkman F S L, Methods for predicting bacterial protein subcellular localization, *Nat Rev Microbiol*, 4 (2006) 741-751.
 - 47 Rappuoli R, Reverse vaccinology, *Cur Opin Microbiol*, 3 (2000) 445-450.
 - 48 Pizza M, Scarlato V, Masignani V, Giuliani M M, Arico B *et al*, Identification of vaccine candidates against serogroup B meningococcus by whole-genome sequencing, *Science*, 287 (2000) 1816-1820.